

BIOLOGICAL RISKS AND AIRBORNE CONTAMINATION IN ROMANIAN MUSEUMS HOSTING TEXTILES HERITAGE OBJECTS

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Abstract: Fungal contamination, presents significant challenges in museum environments for museographers and researchers. Their efforts focus on finding effective measures to prevent the degradation of artifacts but also to minimize exposure risks for staff, including museographers, conservators and guides. Textile heritage objects create ideal conditions for fungal growth. This study evaluated air contamination levels in four Romanian museums using the SAS-100 Surface Air System impactor, with specific culture growth media for detecting fungi. Fungal contamination was detected in most investigated spaces, with the highest levels observed in areas housing heritage items like carpets, curtains, sofas, and costumes. The analysis of the results revealed that, in some museum locations, the occupational exposure limit recommended by the literature, 500 CFU (colony-forming units), was exceeded. Exposure to microfungi poses substantial risks to the health of museum staff. Inhalation of fungal spores or contact with them can lead to respiratory diseases, mycoses and immune system disorders. To ensure a safe environment, both for the heritage objects and for the personnel, proper management of biological agents is vital. Although collective protective measures are preferable, their implementation may be difficult in this case due to the need to protect heritage objects. While identifying appropriate methods of technical collective protection, other measures should be used, like training and individual protective measures. This study aimed to assess the degree of fungal air contamination in certain museum environments and identify the associated occupational risks.

Keywords: fungal contamination, museum, occupational, risk, textiles heritage

1. INTRODUCTION

Museums play an essential role in preserving, researching and promoting national and international cultural heritage. They are spaces dedicated to the conservation and valorization of cultural heritage, but also places of work employees and frequent visits for tourists. They house valuable, sometimes unique collections, which include objects made of organic materials such as paper, textiles, wood, leather, parchment, natural paints, etc. Although they are perceived as stable and controlled environments, museums can become sources of biological contamination [1]. One of the most significant challenges is fungal contamination, often invisible but potentially destructive to heritage objects and to the health of staff.

There is evidence in the literature regarding the risks involved by exposure to fungi in museum spaces. Many fungi are common allergens, but some of them are producers of mycotoxins [2]. These can enter the body through inhalation of spores or through direct skin contact, triggering respiratory tract infections, mycoses, immune system problems, etc. [3]. Species such as *Cladosporium* and *Penicillium* are known to be asthma causative agents. There are species belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* that cause aspergillosis. Exposure to spores of

some species of the genus *Alternaria* can cause asthma and other significant respiratory diseases [4]. Fungal species usually attack objects made of organic materials (such as paper, textiles, wood, paints, leather), degrading them. Mycotic biodegradation is an important problem that results in the damage or even loss of old cultural objects.

In Romania, so far, no occupational exposure limit values have been established for biological agents, although some Member States have set limits for their toxins. The essential difference between biological agents and other dangerous substances lies in their ability to reproduce. Under favorable conditions, a microorganism can multiply considerably in a very short period of time, increasing the risk to the health of exposed workers.

The main regulatory act regulating the protection of workers against the risks related to exposure to biological agents at work is Government Decision no. 1092/2006 on the protection of workers against the risks related to their exposure to biological agents at work. Although it establishes the general framework for the protection of workers exposed to biological agents, there are no official limit values for occupational exposure to fungal bioaerosols [5], transposing the EU Directive 2000/54/CE [6].

Biological agents are classified into 4 risk groups, depending on the importance of the risk of infection they present, as provided for in Annex No. 3 of the mentioned decision and Directive: group 1 – biological agents that are not likely to cause a disease in humans; group 2 – biological agents that can cause a disease in humans and constitute a danger to workers; their spread in the community is unlikely; there is generally effective prophylaxis or treatment; group 3 – biological agents that can cause serious diseases in humans and constitute a serious danger to workers; they may present a risk of spread in the community, but there is generally effective prophylaxis or treatment; group 4 – biological agents that can cause serious diseases in humans and constitute a serious danger to workers; they may present a high risk of spread in the community and there is generally no effective prophylaxis or treatment [5-6].

The classification of biological agents was made according to the degree of virulence expressed in the minimum dose required for a biological agent that can cause an infection, the ease of its spread and the existence of possible preventive or therapeutic measures.

At European level, there are statistics, such as those produced by the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, which show that biological agents represent a significant risk factor in the workplace in general. According to these statistics, in 2001, approximately 1900 cases of occupational diseases were due to exposure to biological agents [7].

In Romania, in 2023, there were 712 museums, of which 143 art museums, 126 archaeology and history museums, 37 science and natural history museums, 22 science and technology museums, 180 ethnography and anthropology museums, 99 specialized museums, 22 general museums, 11 monuments and 72 mixed museums. These museums have a total exhibition area of 2,982,595 m², housing 32,265,422 cultural assets organized in 2687 permanent exhibitions and 4096 temporary exhibitions. The total number of visitors in 2023 was 13,486,145 people. 6,283 people (62.41% women) worked in these museums, of which 1,323 were museographers, 446 conservators, 378 restorers, 216 researchers, 1,197 other specialized personnel, 201 technical personnel and 2,522 administrative and maintenance personnel [8].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Investigated locations

The present study aimed to evaluate the levels of airborne fungal contamination in four museums in Romania, identify spaces with high risk of biological contamination, compare the values obtained with the limits recommended in the specialized literature, highlight the health risks for museum staff and formulate recommendations regarding the efficient management of biological risk in museums.

The study was conducted in four museums in Romania, representing two different geographical and climatic zones, to reflect the diversity of microclimate conditions and the typology of the collections. Each museum holds valuable public collections of textiles made from natural materials (plants, animals or minerals): costumes, flags, carpets, tapestries, upholstered furniture, curtains, paintings on canvas, etc.

For the selection of these study cases, the sampling process was important, but also the presence of textile collections made from organic materials (wool, linen, hemp, silk, cotton, leather, etc.).

For each museum, four types of spaces were investigated:

- Exhibition halls: areas with old textiles and furniture, frequented by visitors;
- Heritage warehouses: spaces with restricted access, where objects are kept in specific microclimate conditions;
- Restoration laboratories: environments with intense activity, where degraded objects are handled;
- Administrative offices: workspaces for staff, relevant for the assessment of indirect occupational exposure.

This diversity of spaces allowed the identification of differences in contamination depending on activity, accessibility and environmental conditions

2.2 Sampling method

The method used was in accordance with the recommendations of the standard SR EN 13098:2020 *Workplace atmosphere. Measurement of microorganisms and microbial compounds in suspension in air. General requirements*. This standard provides criteria for both the selection of sampling equipment and the transport and storage conditions.

Microbiological sampling took place at different times. For the determination of fungal bioaerosols, the SAS-100 (Surface Air System) active impactor was used, a portable device with 219 holes. This equipment allows the sampling of a defined volume of air, which is directed onto selective culture media. Sabouraud medium with chloramphenicol was used, which inhibits the development of bacteria and favors the growth of fungal colonies.

Microbiological sampling took place at different times of usual working days. A total of 56 samples were collected. Depending on the room area, at least one sample was taken in each room using 90 mm diameter Petri dishes with sterile culture medium. For rooms with an area greater than 100 m², at least 2 samples were taken in each room. A 1-minute sampling with 100 liters/minute was used for all samples. All samples were taken from the worker's breathing zone (approx. 1.5 m from the ground). The samples were individualized by labeling and sent to the laboratory in cooled isothermal boxes, protected from direct sunlight [9].

2.3 Sample analysis

The samples were incubated at 25°C for 5 days. The developed fungal colonies were counted and expressed in CFU/m³ (colony forming units per cubic meter of air), applying the J. Maker correction formula, which compensates for the probability that several spores pass through the same sampling orifice.

Morphological analysis of the fungal colonies revealed a significant diversity, indicating the presence of several fungal genera with allergenic or toxic potential. The colonies were classified according to color (white, black, green, gray-white, orange), texture (granular, powdery, woolly), growth rate: fast (colonies visible in 3 days) or slow (mature colonies in 5 days) and appearance: compact or diffuse, with regular or irregular edges.

Morphological analysis allowed a preliminary classification of the colonies and an estimate of the allergenic potential of the identified species.

This diversity suggests the presence of species such as: *Cladosporium* – frequent in spaces with wood and textiles, known allergen; *Penicillium* – present in areas with high

humidity, potential producer of mycotoxins; *Aspergillus* – identifiable by black or green colonies, associated with aspergillosis; *Alternaria* – dark colonies, associated with asthma and severe allergies.

3. RESULTS

Following sample collection and incubation, various values of airborne fungal contamination were obtained, expressed in colony-forming units per cubic meter of air (CFU/m³). Results are presented in Figure 1, where M1, M2, M3 and M4 are the four Romanian museums where measurements were taken and were compared with the limit values recommended by the specialized literature, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Degree of fungal contamination of the air in non-industrial environment

Category	Non-industrial indoor environment (CFU/cm ³ air)
very low	< 25
low	< 100
intermediate	< 500
high	< 2000
very high	> 2000

Source: European Collaborative Action – Indoor Air Quality & its Impact on Man [10]

The absence of universally accepted occupational exposure limits for bioaerosols is due to the lack of well-founded and epidemiologically verified dose-response relationships between biological agents and the health effects they cause. Susceptibility to bioaerosols varies from person to person, as does the intensity of the immune response to certain organisms, complicating any attempt to standardize exposure reference values. Recommendations for reference values are usually related to the clinical manifestation of diseases associated with certain agents. However, these reference values are used to aid in the interpretation of measurement data, even if they fail to provide comprehensive and universally applicable standards [11].

Figure 1. Airborne fungal contamination (CFU/m³) in Romanian museums

In 70% of samples, the values obtained exceeded the threshold of 500 CFU/m³, considered in the literature as the upper limit of safety in indoor spaces frequented by sensitive people. The most affected were poorly ventilated warehouses, laboratories with intense activity, and rooms with old textiles and wooden furniture.

Heritage repositories were the most affected, especially those without automated microclimate control. The presence of leather objects, old textiles and wooden furniture favored the development of fungal colonies. Obtained values are between 140–3983 CFU/m³.

Restoration laboratories showed significant contamination, probably due to the frequent handling of degraded objects and the use of organic materials in the restoration process. Obtained values are between 808–1555 CFU/m³.

Exhibition rooms with directly exposed textiles (tapestries, draperies, costumes) had high levels, especially in areas with intense visitor traffic. Obtained values are between 280–1928 CFU/m³

Administrative offices, although less exposed, recorded values that can become problematic in the event of inadequate ventilation or indirect contamination. Values are between 60–987 CFU/m³

The results obtained confirm the existence of a significant biological risk in museum spaces, especially those housing objects made of organic materials. Daily exposure to fungal bioaerosols can have serious consequences on the health of staff, especially in the case of people with respiratory sensitivity or low immunity.

3.1 Health implications

Biological agents in museums and heritage repositories represent a permanent risk for museum employees who are exposed daily to contact with microorganisms. They can enter the body through the respiratory tract (it is the most likely route of microbial infection). The propagation of bioaerosols can occur over long distances and their infectivity depends on the nature of the contaminant and the state of immune resistance of the person at risk of being contaminated, digestive, due to hygiene deficiencies and practices during the activity, cutaneous: the passage of microorganisms through the skin can occur through accidental penetration (cuts, stings) and in the case of any skin lesions, invisible to the naked eye, mucous: the oral mucosa and upper respiratory tract can be portals for aerosol penetration. Also, the eye, being highly vascularized, represents a route of contamination.

High levels of airborne fungal contamination in museum spaces can have direct effects on the health of staff, in particular:

- Respiratory allergies: rhinitis, conjunctivitis, chronic cough
- Lung diseases: asthma, bronchitis, aspergillosis
- Skin infections: mycoses, dermatitis
- Systemic reactions: chronic fatigue, immune disorders

Laboratory and warehouse staff are exposed to high concentrations of bioaerosols daily, which requires urgent protection and monitoring measures [12].

3.2 Recommendations

To reduce the risks associated with fungal contamination in museum spaces and to protect both cultural heritage and the health of staff, the following measures are recommended [13-15]:

- Periodic monitoring of bioaerosols by implementing a microbiological air monitoring program in all museum spaces, with a frequency established according to the type of heritage collections and the degree of public access.

- Microclimate control by maintaining relative humidity below 50-65% and temperature between 22°C in exhibition and storage spaces and installing automatic climate control and

humidification/dehumidification systems, where necessary [16].

- Efficient ventilation and filtration by ensuring adequate ventilation, with HEPA filters to retain fungal spores and avoiding air stagnation in closed spaces, by using controlled circulation systems.

- Protective equipment for staff by equipping them with protective masks, gloves and gowns, especially in high-risk areas (warehouses, restoration laboratories) and periodic training of employees on biological risks and individual protection measures.

- Periodic sanitation and maintenance by regularly cleaning and disinfecting museum spaces, with antifungal solutions compatible with heritage materials and removing sources of contamination (degraded materials, wet textiles, damaged furniture).

- Development of a national protocol for managing biological risks in museums by creating a specific legislative framework for heritage institutions, including exposure limit values, intervention procedures and safety standards.

- Research and continuous training by supporting interdisciplinary research in the field of biodeterioration of cultural heritage and organizing courses and workshops for specialists in conservation, restoration and occupational health.

The protection of cultural heritage cannot be dissociated from the protection of the health of those who manage it. Museums must become not only conservation spaces, but also examples of good practices in managing biological risks, by adopting proactive measures, based on scientific evidence and international standards.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study conducted in four Romanian museums highlighted a real and persistent biological risk posed by airborne fungal contamination. Although museums are often perceived as controlled environments, our results demonstrate that, without rigorous monitoring and preventive measures, these spaces can become prone to fungal growth, adversely affecting both staff health and the preservation of cultural heritage. The presence of organic materials such as textiles, paper, leather, and wood, combined with favorable humidity and temperature, and inadequate ventilation in some places, fosters fungal proliferation. Several sampled locations exhibited contamination levels exceeding the 500 CFU/m³ threshold—the upper safety limit for indoor air—indicating significant risks to both personnel and patrimonial objects.

Beyond these immediate concerns, fungal contamination presents systemic challenges that merit greater attention. The deterioration of heritage objects represents not only a material loss but also a rupture in the cultural memory of communities. A damaged tapestry, degraded manuscript, or destroyed traditional costume signifies a break in the identity chain of a people. Therefore, managing biological risks must be an integral part of preventive conservation policies, heritage digitization efforts, and museum emergency planning. Achieving this requires an interdisciplinary approach, engaging microbiologists, conservators, epidemiologists, architects, environmental engineers, and occupational health experts. Only through such collaboration can a sustainable and replicable model for biological protection in museums be established at both national and international levels.

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